

Clinicoepidemiological Presentation and Management of Ophthalmological Symptoms among Patients with Otorhinolaryngology, Head and Neck Diseases

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Ophthalmological presentations among otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases are very common and the awareness is paramount in patients' effective care. This study aimed at determined the clinicoepidemiological presentation and management of ophthalmological symptoms among patients with ear, nose, throat, head and neck diseases. **Materials and Methods:** This was an hospital based prospective study carried out in the Ear, Nose and Throat department of Ekiti state university teaching hospital Ado Ekiti, Nigeria. Data were obtained by using assisted self-administered structured questionnaire on sociodemographic features, ophthalmological and Otorhinolaryngological symptoms. **Results:** The patients' peak age group was 41-50 years in 25.3%. There were 61.4% males with male to female ratio of 1.6:1. Family physician were the commonest source of referral in 38.6%. The most common Otorhinolaryngology, head and neck symptom was nasal obstruction in 50.6%. The most common ophthalmological symptom among the study patients was proptosis in 56.6%. Nasal polyps was the most common Otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases in 33.7%. The most common diagnostic and therapeutic requested investigations among the patients was 80.7% anthral endoscopy. The commonest pre hospital treatment received by the patients was 26.5% herbal consumption/ over the counter drugs. Major surgical treatment among the patients was 33.7% intranasal polypectomy. **Conclusion:** Advanced and poorly managed otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases usually has ophthalmological symptoms. Otorhinolaryngologist and ophthalmologist must look beyond their speciality during patient management.

Keywords: *Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology, Head Neck Symptoms*

INTRODUCTION:

Anatomical position of the orbit and its content are very close to the nose, paranasal sinuses and pharynx. Possibility of orbital involvement and associated orbital pathology is very high in otorhinolaryngological and ophthalmological practice.¹⁻³ Also orbital complications may also arises from delayed or poorly management of these organs.⁴

Common ear, nose and throat diseases with orbital complications are inflammatory, neoplastic and polyps.² Infections inflammatory disease like acute and chronic rhinosinusitis leading to emergency orbital cellulitis and abscess which needs early diagnosis and aggressive management. Delayed or late treatment usually leads to poor outcome such as irreversible blindness due to optic nerve compression. Orbital extension of sinonasal

tumours and polyps causes compression and displacement of its content. Compression of ocular muscles, vessels and nerves presenting as diplopia, blurring of vision, proptosis, ophthalmoplegia and blindness.

Orbital complications from the nose and paranasal sinuses diseases extension could arise from direct spread and bony destruction.⁶⁻⁹ Spreading via the nerves supplying the orbital content and through nasolacrimal apparatus are also possible. Nose and paranasal sinuses disorders may extend to the orbit by natural pathway such as fissures and foramina of the bony orbit.

Ophthalmological Manifestations of ear, nose and throat disorders in most cases is an indication of extent of extension and aggressiveness of the pathology. Most of these disorders with orbital complications are often difficult to treat. There is paucity of literature on ophthalmological manifestations of otorhinolaryngological diseases in our environment. This study aimed at determined the clinicoepidemiological presentation and management of ophthalmological symptoms among patients with ear, nose, throat, head and neck diseases among patients seen and treated in ear, nose and throat department.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This hospital based prospective study was carried out in the Ear, Nose and Throat department of Ekiti state university teaching hospital Ado Ekiti, Nigeria. This study was carried out over a period of ten years from February 2011 to January 2021.

All patients in all gender and age groups that presented to ear, nose and throat department with ophthalmological presentations arising from primary ear, nose, throat, head and neck diseases were included in the study. Informed consent were obtained from patients, parents and guardian while only consented participants were enrolled into the study. They were assured of confidentiality.

Data were obtained by using assisted self-administered structured questionnaire on sociodemographic features. Detailed information on ophthalmic, ear, nose and throat symptoms were taken. Detailed examination findings on ocular, ear, nose and throat were documented. Appropriate investigations including imaging and microbiological studies were requested and findings were documented. Ophthalmological and ear, nose and throat diagnoses were also documented. Management including source of referral, prior treatment, treatment interventions and outcome with complications were recorded.

Observed orbital complications of sinusitis were categorized according to Chandler's classification of orbital infections.¹⁰

Stage 1: Periorbital cellulitis/ preseptal cellulitis.

Stage II: Orbital cellulitis/post septal cellulitis

Stage III: Sub periosteal abscess.

Stage IV: Orbital abscess.

Stage V: Cavernous sinus thrombosis.

Inclusion criteria was all consecutive patients attending ear, nose and throat department with various ophthalmological symptoms secondary to primary ear, nose and throat diseases.

Exclusion criteria was patients with primary ophthalmological disease. Also patients presenting with ear, nose and throat complaints without ophthalmological symptoms.

Data obtained were collated and analyzed using SPSS version 22.0. The data were further expressed in percentage, table and charts.

Ethical clearance were sought for and obtained from ethical committee of the institution.

RESULTS:

All the patients with otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases in this research work had ophthalmological symptoms and signs. The highest number of affected patients were in the age group 41-50 years with 21 (25.3%) and this was followed by age group 31-40 years with 17 (20.5%). The patients' age ranges from 2 years old to 76 years old. This is illustrated in table 1.

There were 51 (61.4%) males and 32 (38.6%) females in our study. The male to female ratio was 1.6:1. Christian faith accounted for 74 (89.2%) while Muslim faith accounted for 8 (9.6%). Urban dwellers and rural dwellers were 47 (56.6%) and 36 (43.4%) respectively. Commonest level of education among the patients was secondary in 29 (34.9%) followed by 26 (31.3%) primary and 18 (21.7%) tertiary. This is demonstrated in table 2.

Family physician were the commonest source of referral to ear, nose and throat department which accounted for 32 (38.6%). This was followed by ophthalmology and general surgeon in 20 (24.2%) and 13 (15.7%) respectively. Self-reporting cases occurred in 11(13.3%). As it is shown in figure 1.

The most common otorhinolaryngology, head and neck symptoms was nasal obstruction in 42 (50.6%) and this was followed by nasal discharge, bouts of sneezing and epistaxis in 36 (43.4%), 34 (41.0%) and 26 (31.3%) respectively. There were 12 (14.5%) facial asymmetry and 12 (14.5%) olfactory dysfunction among studied patients. In this study the most common ophthalmological symptom among the study patients was proptosis in 47 (56.6%) followed by periorbital oedema 31 (37.3%). There were 27 (32.5%) redness of the eyes, 14 (16.9%) ocular pain and 13 (15.7%) reduced vision. This is further illustrated in table 3.

Nasal polyps in 28 (33.7%) was the most common otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases responsible

for ophthalmological presentations among the patients. This findings was followed by rhinosinusitis, sinonasal tumours and Bell's palsy in 18 (21.%),10 (12.0%) and 9 (10.8%) respectively. There were 4 (4.8%) otitis media, 4 (4.8%) nasopharyngeal carcinoma and 3 (3.6%) thyroid diseases. This is illustrated in table 4.

The most common diagnostic requested investigations among the patients was 67 (80.7%) diagnostic nasal endoscopy. This was followed by CT scan of the paranasal sinuses and MRI in 51 (61.4%) and 23 (27.7%) respectively. Other investigations included 17 (20.5%) ultrasound scan and 11 (13.3%) microbiology. This is demonstrated in figure 2.

In this study nil pre hospital treatment was initiated in 47 (56.6%). The commonest pre hospital treatment received by the patients was 22 (26.5%) herbal consumption/ over the counter drugs. Other included prayer in 18 (21.7%). In the hospital, there were medical treatment in all the patients with surgical treatment in 57 (68.7%) patients. As shown in table 5.

Major surgical treatment among the patients was 28 (33.7%) intranasal polypectomy. This was followed by 16 (19.3%) functional endoscopic sinus surgery, 11 (13.3%) EUA and Biopsy with 9 (10.8%) external frontoethmoidectomy. Thyroidectomy and mastoidectomy were performed in 2 (2.4%) each. This is illustrated in figure 3.

Table 1: Age distribution among the patients

Age groups (years)	Number	Percentage (%)
1-10	6	7.2
11-20	7	8.4
21-30	12	14.5
31-40	17	20.5
41-50	21	25.3
51-60	9	10.8
61-70	8	9.6
>70	3	3.6
Total	83	

Table 2: Sociodemographic features

Sociodemographic features	Number	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Males	51	61.4
Females	32	38.6
Religion		
Christian	74	89.2
Islam	8	9.6
Traditional	1	1.2
Residential		
Rural	36	43.4
Urban	47	56.6
Level of education		
No formal	10	12.1
Primary	26	31.3
Secondary	29	34.9
Tertiary	18	21.7

Figure 1: Source of referral

Table 3: Ophthalmological and Otorhinolaryngology, head and neck symptoms

Symptoms	Number	Percentage (%)
Otorhinolaryngological Symptoms		
Nasal obstruction	42	50.6
Epistaxis	26	31.3
Nasal discharge	36	43.4
Facial swelling	8	9.6
Sneezing	34	41.0
Olfactory dysfunction	12	14.5
Ear discharge	6	7.2
Facial asymmetry	12	14.5
Neck swelling	6	7.2
Ophthalmological symptoms		
Redness of eyes	27	32.5
Reduced vision	13	15.7
Proptosis	47	56.6
Diplopia	9	10.8
Periorbital Oedema	31	37.3
Ocular pain	14	16.9

Figure 2: Investigations among the patients

Table 4: Otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diagnosis

Diagnosis	Number	Percentage (%)
Sinonasal tumours	10	12.0
Rhinosinusitis	18	21.7
Fungal rhinosinusitis	2	2.4
Facial infections	2	2.4
Fibrous Dysplasia	1	1.2
Otitis Media	4	4.8
Nasopharyngeal carcinoma	4	4.8
	28	33.7
Nasal polyps	3	3.6
Thyroid disease	1	1.2
Carcinoma parotid	1	1.2
Frontoethmoidal mucocele	9	10.8
Bell's Palsy		

Table 5: Management of the patients

Management	Number	Percentage (%)
Prior treatment		
Nil	47	56.6
Herb/ over the counter drugs	22	26.5
Prayer	18	21.7
Scarification	9	10.8
Treatment interventions		
Medical	83	100
Surgical	57	68.7

DISCUSSION:

In this study of presentation of ophthalmological symptoms among patients with otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases the presentation were noticed among all studied age groups. The prevalence rate was highest in the fourth decades of life. This distribution concurred with findings reported in other studies.^{11, 12}

There was male preponderance among the patients. This results was contrary to findings reported other studies.^{11, 12} Preponderance male sex distribution was reported in similar study has been inconsistent.² This study with others revealed inconvenience sex distribution.

In this study of presentation of ophthalmological symptoms among patients with otorhinolaryngology, head and neck disease, family physician were the commonest source of referral to ear, nose and throat department for expert review and management. This arises as a result of family physician were the first contact in patients seeking medical treatment and they were mainly referred due Otorhinolaryngological

disorders. Following family physician were ophthalmologist and general surgeon as a results their clinical findings in the ocular and neck presentations respectively. Self-reporting cases occurred subsequent to advanced or poorly treated sinonasal tumours and inflammatory disorders.

In this research work, nasal polyps was the most common otorhinolaryngology, head and neck diseases that responsible for ophthalmological symptoms among the patients. This is followed by rhinosinusitis arising from infections and allergic reaction. Similar findings of tumours as predominant aetiology was reported in other studies.¹²⁻¹⁵ Contrary work revealed inflammatory rhinosinusitis as the commonest causes.^{2, 12} The ophthalmological presentations in nasal polyps and other tumours arises from contiguous extension into the orbit and displacing orbital contents leading to proptosis. Inflammatory disorders in rhinosinusitis causes ocular symptoms from venous congestion and inflammatory

exudate in the rigid orbital cage with subsequent proptosis.

Commoner ophthalmological symptoms in this study was proptosis and similar results was reported in other studies.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ This results is contrary to reported findings in previous research work.^{19, 20} This findings was due to poorly managed rhinosinusitis with infection spreading out to orbital contents resulting into cellulitis or abscess. Advanced sinonasal tumours with bony destruction and orbital extension causing ophthalmoplegia from extraocular muscles compression. Bell's palsy also present with paralyzed eyelid as part of clinical presentation. Through the inferior orbital fissure in advanced nasopharyngeal carcinoma spread into the orbit with proptosis and ophthalmoplegia as ophthalmological presentations. Neck diseases from thyrotoxicosis leads to thyroid eyes.

Proper management of otorhinolaryngological, head and neck diseases with ophthalmological symptoms required appropriate and timely investigations. The investigation play a crucial role in the management of patients with ophthalmological symptoms of these diseases.² Radiological image and ultrasound scan plays a crucial role in delineating the extents of orbital complications. CT scan and MRI also play crucial role to surgical planning prior to surgery for many of our patients. Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy, Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology and Examination Under Anaesthesia with Biopsy were for both diagnostic and effective surgical planning. They were also done to differentiate tumours types prior to definitive surgery. To identify the offending organisms in inflammatory rhinosinusitis microscopy, culture and sensitivity including mycology were requested.

Herbal interventions and over the counter medication prior to hospital presentation were the main indication for late presentation in the hospital. In this study medical treatment were offered to inflammatory conditions with cellulitis without abscess formation. Surgical management were offered to inflammatory conditions with abscess or tumours. Surgical interventions depends on nature and extents of nasal mass, types of paranasal sinuses affected, number of paranasal sinuses affected and extents of orbital complications. Intranasal polypectomy and functional endoscopic sinus surgery were the commonest surgical technique. This is because ethmoid sinuses were the most commonly in our study of Otolaryngology, head and neck diseases with ophthalmological symptoms.

CONCLUSIONS:

In otorhinolaryngology and ophthalmology practices some patients present with advanced and poorly managed otorhinolaryngology diseases with ophthalmological symptoms. There is need for a high

index of suspicion from both specialty to look beyond their specialty during their patient management. A team work between the otorhinolaryngologist and ophthalmologist is highly essential in effective management and successful outcome such patients.

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Conflicts of interest:

There are no conflicts of interest. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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